

HERCCULES

full CCUS chain demonstration

COMMUNITY ACCEPTANCE FINDINGS FROM FIRST REGIONAL SURVEY

Deliverable D8.3

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D8.3 Community Acceptance Findings from first regional survey

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This Deliverable D8.3 of HERCCULES WP8 on Social Perception and Community Engagement reports on the state of community acceptance of CCUS. It focuses on two regions in the two countries studied in HERCCULES, Greece and Italy. The regions selected are those where CO₂ storage is being developed in relation to the HERCCULES project, i.e. Kavala and Thasos (part of the Eastern Macedonia and Thrace region in Greece) and Emilia-Romagna (in Italy). Community acceptance was measured through standardised surveys in the regions (sample sizes of 506 and 498 respondents in Eastern Macedonia and Thrace and Emilia-Romagna respectively). This regional view is compared with a national perspective in order to place the regional results in a broader context. The representative national samples consist of 1016 respondents in Greece and 1022 respondents in Italy. Deliverable 8.2 is part of the exploratory analyses together with D8.1 ('Analysis of policy alignment including country case studies') and the results of the detailed regional profiles, the results of which are published in D8.2. Based on this exploration, an engagement and participation strategy for the HERCCULES project will be designed and implemented.

The total number of respondents in the four surveys conducted in spring 2024 is N=3042. The results suggest that the socio-political acceptance of CCUS as a technology option to reduce CO₂ emissions differs between the samples. Italian respondents are more positive (>70% positive). In Greece, the evaluation by respondents in the national sample is lower than in Italy (48% positive) and acceptance is even lower in Eastern Macedonia and Thrace (41% positive). The reported level of familiarity with CCUS technologies is low in all samples, with more than 50% of respondents stating that they had never heard of it.

We conclude that an important task for public engagement and participation is to increase familiarity with the technology. Other insights from the survey include lines of argument on which a discussion about CCUS could be built, such as societal agreement on the need to tackle climate change and to see energy-intensive industries as important for the region and country.

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	
CCUS	Carbon capture, utilisation, and storage
CCU	Carbon capture and utilisation
CCS	Carbon capture and storage
NGO	Non-governmental organisation

2 INTRODUCTION

This deliverable reports the findings from the first wave of surveys in Task 8.3. Together with Task 8.2 these two tasks form the outcomes of the exploratory phase in the HERCCULES project which aim at providing an extensive characterisation of the study regions as a preparation of the engagement phase. While Task 8.2 takes a case study approach with a combination of methodological approaches with strong qualitative elements (document and media analyses, interviews), **Task 8.3 employs a quantitative survey approach to investigate in detail the status of community acceptance of carbon capture, utilisation, and storage (CCUS) in Greece and Italy.** At its current stage, the empirical basis combines a representative national (around 1000 respondents per country) with a regional survey (around 500 respondents). The regional survey will be repeated towards the end of the project. The regions under study are Eastern Macedonia and Thrace (Greece) and Emilia-Romagna (Italy) and are the projected regions where CO₂-storage is supposed to take place within HERCCULES. Besides acceptance evaluations, the questionnaires measure a number of key attitudinal and personal dimensions, such as familiarity, perceived impacts, trust, fairness perception, or preference for alternatives. Besides acquiring a deeper understanding of the situation in the regions, the surveys also serve as a starting point for discussions in the engagement phase and will be shared with communities and stakeholders within the regions.

Previous research has shown that CO₂ storage is usually the most critical step in the CCUS chain (e.g. Upham & Roberts, 2011); therefore, and due to resource limitations, the project team decided to focus the engagement and participation activities of WP8 and hence also the surveys specifically on those regions where storage sites are being developed. As a result, the regions hosting some of the other facilities that are part of HERCCULES such as CO₂ capture are only included if they are close to the storage sites which are under development.

In the following section of this deliverable, we shortly report on the more general state of knowledge on perceptions and acceptance of CCUS. Afterwards, the specific methodology for implementing and analysing the survey is explained (Section 4) before we move on to the results (Section 5). The deliverable closes with a discussion and conclusions for the project (Section 6).

3 PERCEPTION AND ACCEPTANCE OF CCUS

3.1 PUBLIC AWARENESS AND FAMILIARITY WITH CCUS

Generally, public awareness of CCUS technologies is low across European countries (Dütschke et al., 2022; European Commission, 2011; Jones et al., 2017). There is some variation in awareness levels, such that awareness and knowledge tend to be higher in countries that are more actively involved in CCUS technologies, such as Norway (Whitmarsh et al., 2019). The implication of these low levels of awareness is that current perceptions of CCUS technologies are not as stable as for established technologies, but may change dynamically depending on public debates.

3.2 ACCEPTANCE DIMENSIONS: SOCIO-POLITICAL AND COMMUNITY ACCEPTANCE

When looking at perceptions in terms of social acceptance, three dimensions or perspectives are usually considered (Upham et al., 2015): The first dimension, **socio-political acceptance**, refers to the general social climate towards a technology or innovation within a society, i.e. it refers to typical discussions about an issue or socially desirable opinions. The second dimension, **community acceptance**, is relevant when it comes to siting decisions and refers to the attitudes and behaviours of residents, e.g. individuals who live or work close to an installation and might (actively) endorse or

oppose it. The third dimension relates to **market acceptance** and describes the level of support and interest of a technology by actors in the relevant market, i.e. investors, supply and demand side. As this deliverable focuses on characterising the regions in which storage is developed in HERCCULES, the focus is on socio-political and community acceptance.

Socio-political acceptance interacts with community acceptance such that individuals who support a technology in general are also more likely to support it locally and vice versa. In the case of community acceptance, people usually perceive themselves as being directly affected by the development, which tends to motivate them to act on their opinions. Affectedness refers to the potential benefits and risks associated with the development — and may be linked to the specific site under discussion, its relevance to natural or cultural heritage. Furthermore, local conditions and personal context also influence community acceptance, thus, possibly citizens oppose a local development due to concerns that the chosen site is unsuitable if it affects valued areas such as natural heritage or if they feel unfairly treated by project developers.

3.3 ACCEPTANCE OF CCUS

Some research focuses on CCUS while some studies only consider carbon capture and storage (CCS) or carbon capture and utilisation (CCU) respectively. Partly these streams have even developed a bit independently of each other.

L'Orange Seigo et al. (2014) summarise the early literature on the perception and acceptance of CCS, drawing on 42 papers. This research mainly focuses on *socio-political* and *community acceptance*. As noted above, exposure rates and knowledge levels of the populations studied were generally low. Typically, studies address this by providing information about the technology before inquiring the survey respondents' opinions on CCS (ter Mors et al., 2013). Levels of *socio-political* acceptance were often moderate, neither specifically positive nor negative. Newer studies find more favourable levels of acceptance (Whitmarsh et al., 2019 in a study across five countries).

Perceived risks and benefits were the main predictors of variation in socio-political acceptance (L'Orange Seigo et al., 2014). Potential risks include leaks or blowouts of CO₂, including induced seismicity; local impacts, e.g. on property values or tourism; and CCS as an unsustainable solution to maintain harmful industries. On the positive side, the main perceived benefit is the contribution to climate change mitigation, and sometimes also that CCS could enable a smoother transition and bring local economic benefits. The basic rationale for CCS tends to be that there is an understanding that climate change is a problem that needs to be tackled; this is the case for large majorities in various societies, as confirmed by the studies reviewed.

Several studies report public opposition to CCS project initiatives (e.g. Akerboom et al., 2021), however there are also successfully implemented projects (Dütschke, 2010; Rothkirch & Ejderyan, 2021). Studies on prospective projects point to mixed findings — e.g. Whitmarsh et al. (2019) find more favourable opinions for local publics in their multi-country study, while Braun (2017) find the contrary for Germany in a comparison of regions with or without the potential to develop CCUS. For actual projects, i.e. for community acceptance, the review by L'Orange Seigo et al. (2014) outlines — based on Oltra et al. (2012) — that trust in the developer, the quality of public engagement activities (see also Mors & van Leeuwen, 2023), and the perceived need for the facility are most relevant. In addition, there is some evidence that previous local experience with similar industries may be important (L'Orange Seigo et al., 2014).

This is consistent with studies that have examined whether the overall CCS scenario and its components matter, such as the source of CO₂ that is decarbonised with CCS. With a representative German sample, Dütschke et al. (2016) found that CCS is viewed more positively when the captured

CO₂ is produced by a biomass power plant or heavy industry than when it is produced by a coal-fired power plant. Further analyses in this study showed that the general attitude towards the respective CO₂ source is most important for the overall evaluation of CCS and that the general attitude of the CO₂ source depends on its perceived relevance for Germany. Whitmarsh et al. (2019) found that CCS is viewed more positively in combination with bioenergy than with shale gas, underground coal gasification or heavy industry; scenarios that combine carbon capture with use, i.e. CCU, are viewed more positively than without. This is confirmed in studies by Arning et al. (2019) and Oltra et al. (2022).

The CCU literature has hardly looked in more detail into community acceptance in reference to actually planned or implemented projects and is mainly based on broader surveys as outlined above (Jones et al., 2017).

3.4 PRIOR RESEARCH ON GREECE AND ITALY

Greece and Italy are countries that do not have a strong history of pilot projects involving CC(U)S. Few earlier studies have analysed these two countries of interest, and none — to the best of our knowledge the regions of interest in this study, Eastern Macedonia and Thrace, and Emilia-Romagna. One of the few studies available, that includes the two countries, is the Eurobarometer on CCS by the European Commission (2011). Here only 5% of respondents stated that they have ever heard about CCS.

One region from Greece, Western Macedonia, is part of the Horizon Europe funded research project PilotSTRATEGY¹. The project undertook an exploration of the community acceptance of CCS based on documents, interviews, and a regional survey in 2022 for regions that are currently explored for their suitability for CO₂ storage (Dütschke et al., 2022). From a stakeholder perspective, the main message was an openness to further pursue CCS as an option in the region — especially in the wake of the declining coal industry. CCS, possibly in conjunction with the development of a hydrogen economy, could help to create jobs in the region. Overall they were optimistic that citizens in the region would support its development, if it was combined with a good engagement strategy and minimal environmental impact. In the survey, respondents from Western Macedonia showed a medium level of familiarity with CCS compared to regions in other countries (France, Spain, Poland, Portugal) surveyed in parallel. More than 10% said they knew what it was, just over half said they had heard of it without further knowledge, and just over a third said they had never heard of it. The Greek respondents' overall assessment of CCS as a technological option to tackle climate change is mixed. Almost 40% say it could be a (very) good option, but almost a third think it is a (very) bad option. Together with another country surveyed in parallel, Spain, this is the lowest overall rating for CCS. At the local level, however, acceptance is much more positive, with more than half of respondents supporting it and less than 20% finding it unacceptable.

4 METHODS

In the following, the methods used to assess the community acceptance of the potential implementation of the CCUS technology in the study areas in Greece and Italy are presented. This includes both the first wave of regional surveys and the national surveys. A second wave of regional surveys will be implemented in year five of the HERCCULES project to assess developments in public perceptions during the project lifetime.

¹ <https://pilotstrategy.eu/>

4.1 QUESTIONNAIRE AND STUDY PROCEDURE

The aim of the first wave of regional surveys in Eastern Macedonia and Thrace (Greece) and Emilia-Romagna (Italy) was to investigate in detail the state of *community acceptance of the local implementation of CCUS technology, which includes primarily the capture and offshore storage of CO₂ (CCS)*. By comparing the results of the regional surveys, the current perceptions of CO₂ storage pilots among the general public in the regions were analysed. Furthermore, the results of national surveys in Greece and Italy serve as a baseline for the regional results. By contrasting the regional and national results, the societal readiness of CCUS projects in the specific regions and in the countries as a whole were assessed, relating findings on *community acceptance* to those on *socio-political acceptance*.

For the first wave of regional surveys and the national surveys, the initial idea was to conduct them online with sample sizes of 500 respondents (living in the vicinity of the respective storage site) for the regional surveys and 1,000 respondents for the national surveys. The recruitment of participants was carried out by market research companies as subcontractors. These companies specialise in household surveys and have access to panels of potential respondents that they can leverage. While in Greece, we had separate market research companies recruiting participants for the regional and the national survey, in Italy both recruitments were carried out by the same market research company. In the regional surveys, definition of the sampling regions had to account for low population rates in the immediate vicinity of the storage sites and lack of coverage in the market research companies' contact data, leading to a wider definition of the regions. Taking the definition of the regions involved and the specificities of each country in terms of research practices and services available from market research companies into account, the research team decided to use online sampling for the national surveys and for the regional survey in Italy. For the regional survey in Greece a combination of phone and online sampling was chosen. The length of the survey also had to be adapted accordingly, with a shorter questionnaire for the regional survey in Greece. Table 1 provides an overview of the final implementation.

Table 1: Overview on study research design and sample sizes.

Sample region/country	Final sample size	Type of provision	Length
Eastern Macedonia and Thrace	N=506	Phone/Online	10 min
Greece	N=1016	Online	10 min
Emilia-Romagna	N=498	Online	10 min
Italy	N=1022	Online	10 min

The research team developed a modular questionnaire with a common, identical core across all surveys to allow for comparison between countries and between regional and national levels. In addition, some region and country specific questions were added, as well as some additional topics for the longer online questionnaires. The topics covered in each of the regional and national questionnaires are presented in Table 2. The common core of the questionnaire is documented in Table A1 in the annex.

Table 2: Overview on the survey content.

Topics in the questionnaire	Eastern Macedonia and Thrace	Greece	Emilia-Romagna	Italy
Socio-economic variables	x	x	x	x
Place attachment	(x)	-	x	-
Topics of concern	-	x	x	x
Perception regarding climate change	x	x	x	x
Attitudes towards industry	x	x	x	x
Familiarity with CCUS	x	x	x	x
(Informed) acceptance of CCUS	(x)	x	(x)	x
Expected impacts of CCUS implementation	x	x	x	x
Acceptance conditions	x	x	x	x
Preferences for alternative approaches	-	x	x	x
Expectations regarding the process	(x)	x	x	x
Trust in societal stakeholders	x	x	x	x
Preferred involvement of societal stakeholders	-	x	x	x
Preferred involvement in the process	x	-	x	-

Note: x = Included in respective questionnaire, (x) = Partly included in respective questionnaire, - = Not included in respective questionnaire.

For the implementation of the mixed phone and online approach in the regional survey in Greece we had to slightly adapt the explanatory text of the CCUS technology, as no graphics could be presented in the phone survey. All surveys were conducted in the national languages and fieldwork started in February 2024 and was completed in each sample by April at the latest. Data analysis was carried out in RStudio and focused mainly on descriptive statistics and comparisons between countries and between regional and national levels.

4.2 STUDY AREAS

The empirical basis of this study is formed by representative household surveys in two countries, namely Greece and Italy. **The surveys are conducted in regions currently under examination for implementing CCUS pilot projects in HERCCULES.** Findings regarding the public perceptions within the regions are further contrasted with assessments by the general public in the respective countries.

The two areas under study in the HERCCULES project, i.e. the **Kavala and Thasos** region in Greece and **Emilia-Romagna** in Italy exhibit significant differences in their economic, political, and social landscapes. **Kavala and Thasos**, characterised by its rural economy reliant on agriculture, fisheries,

and tourism, along with substantial input from the fossil fuel industry, faces economic challenges with a lower GDP per capita than the national average. The region's political environment is centralised, with decisions regarding CCUS made in Athens, limiting local influence. In contrast, **Emilia-Romagna** is one of Europe's most industrialised and affluent regions, with high employment rates and incomes. Its decentralised political system may grant regional authorities more autonomy to facilitate proactive engagement with CCUS activities. For detailed regional profiles, see D8.2.

4.3 SAMPLE

Representativeness of the samples was aimed at in terms of **gender**, **age** (using four categories), and **education**. The hard quotas set up for this purpose were not crossed and were based on either regional or national statistics, depending on the level of analysis. In the regional surveys, the quota for the respondents' educational level was based on national statistics due to limited data availability. Accordingly, this criterion was set as a soft quota, allowing a higher tolerance compared to hard quotas. Finally, the ratio of residents in the respective administrative units was also set as a soft quota.

Table 3: Overview on socio-demographic variables and the respective shares in the final samples.

Socio-demographic variables		Eastern Macedonia and Thrace	Greece	Emilia-Romagna	Italy
Gender	Female	51%	52%	50%	53%
	Male	49%	48%	49%	47%
	Non-binary	-	0%	0%	0%
Age group (in years) ²	18-29	14%	19%	15%	14%
	30-49	31%	43%	35%	31%
	50-59	-	-	21%	-
	50-69	35%	38%	-	35%
	60+	-	-	30%	-
	70+	21%	1%	-	20%
Educational level	University degree or comparable	44%	45%	28%	26%
Place of residence		All of the queried administrative units are represented.			

The samples drawn (see Table 3) were intended to be representative, but not all quotas were fully met. As outlined above, only few socio-economic variables could be used for quota sampling and in

² In Eastern Macedonia and Thrace, Greece, and Italy the following four age groups were used: 18-29 years; 30-49 years; 50-69 years; 70+ years. In Emilia-Romagna the following four age groups were used: 18-29 years; 30-49 years; 50-59 years; 60+ years.

terms of age distribution these were only partially met. This is due to the services offered by market research companies, whose panels do not cover a high share of older individuals. Thus, while the samples cover the targeted gender distribution in the population well in terms of the quota set, this is only partially true for the age distribution in the four categories. While in Greece the oldest category is underrepresented, in Emilia-Romagna the low number of older individuals in the panel led to a modified definition of the two oldest categories, thus limiting comparability. Hence, the results obtained need to be interpreted with some caution, which is why the comparison of the samples is an important part of the interpretation.

5 RESULTS

In the following, the survey results are presented. The summary figures presented in this section show the relative frequencies of the response options (excluding the 'don't know' option, which is discussed in Section 5.10 in detail). For the purpose of comparability, only topics that were asked in all or most of the regions, i.e. the common identical core of the modular questionnaire, are presented. Due to methodological differences between online and phone surveys, the length of the questionnaire of the regional survey in Greece, which combined both approaches, had to be adjusted and some items had to be omitted. Consequently, results for some of the reported topics are not available for the regional survey in Greece.

This section is structured as follows: First, we report on the respondents' familiarity with CCUS (Section 5.1), followed by their (informed) acceptance of this technology option (Section 5.2), as well as the expected local changes a potential deployment of CCUS would bring to the study areas (Section 5.3), and the conditions for acceptance of its deployment (Section 5.4). Then, we present results on the expectations regarding the potential implementation process (Section 5.5), the respondents' trust in societal actors (Section 5.6), and their preferences regarding the involvement of these actors (Section 5.7). Furthermore, we report the results on the respondents' preferences for alternative approaches to mitigate climate change (Section 5.8) and provide an overview of respondents' attitudes and sentiments on issues that might be related to the acceptance of CCUS (Section 5.9). Finally, we discuss the observed uncertainties in the respondents' response behaviours (Section 5.10).

5.1 FAMILIARITY WITH CCUS

In the surveyed countries, we find that the reported **levels of familiarity are rather low** (see Figure 1), with less than 13% of respondents in all samples reporting to have heard of CCUS and to know what it is. The results for the share of respondents that don't know what CCUS is but have heard of the technology vary between countries. While in Emilia-Romagna (>44%), the share of respondents that have at least heard of the technology is similar to the share among the general population in Italy (>44%), there is a statistically significant difference between Eastern Macedonia and Thrace (>48%) and the national general public in Greece (>58%). Interestingly, the relatively high proportion of respondents in Greece who had already heard of the technology is not accompanied by higher levels of familiarity compared to the other samples.

Figure 1: Familiarity with CCUS.

When asked where respondents who had already heard of CCUS got their information about the technology, many said they had heard about it in the media (mainly TV) or on the internet. Others got their information from personal contacts, such as friends or relatives, or at work. The question about the source of their information about CCUS was designed to be open-ended, with no pre-defined categories.

As CCUS is an unfamiliar topic, it is also relevant to look at the shares of respondents that answered 'I don't know'. It is worth noting that up to 12% of respondents chose the *don't know* option in the CCUS related questions presented in Sections 5.2 and 5.3. In general, the shares of *don't know* responses are not included in the shares presented in this section and therefore reduce them relatively. More details on the distribution of *don't know* responses in the sample are given in Section 5.10.

5.2 (INFORMED) ACCEPTANCE OF CCUS

In the surveys, we asked the respondents to evaluate CCUS (*socio-political acceptance*), which was introduced as a technology option to mitigate CO₂ emissions, and to indicate their level of *community acceptance* for the potential implementation of this technology in the respective study areas, i.e. Kavala and Thasos in Greece and Emilia-Romagna in Italy. To enable the respondents to make an informed assessment, we provided them with basic information about CCUS and the project activities in the national languages. Due to the limited length of the questionnaire and in order not to bias respondents' answers, the provision of detailed information on the benefits of CCUS and the likelihood of commonly associated risks was not a viable option. Instead, our aim was to provide as neutral information as possible. In the following, the common identical information as provided in the questionnaires is presented. In addition, the online surveys featured an explanatory figure (see Figure 2) as well as a map of the area in which the CCUS technology is investigated. In the national surveys, where familiarity with the respective study areas was expected to be lower, the map had to be adjusted accordingly to show the location of the study area in the respective country.

To tackle **climate change**, governments and companies are exploring various **mitigation options**. These options include **Carbon Capture, Utilisation, and Storage (CCUS)**, which **reduces carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions**, mainly from existing industrial plants. CO₂ is the main cause of human-induced global warming and the associated climate crisis.

The basic mechanism is to capture CO₂ from the source (industrial plants that emit large amounts of CO₂ during production). The captured CO₂ can then be used as a feedstock for the manufacture of other products, which is referred to as **Carbon Capture and Utilisation (CCU)**. Some of the emitted CO₂ can then be re-captured and re-used in a circular manner. Alternatively, the captured CO₂ can be permanently stored deep underground, which is referred to as **Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS)**.

Figure 2: Explanatory figure on CCUS provided in the questionnaires.

In addition to the above information, the questionnaires indicated that the project evaluates CCUS primarily in terms of storage of CO₂ (CCS). We further described that the current research project supports the development of small scale underground storage of CO₂ from a scientific viewpoint. This includes an economic and environmental evaluation as well as involving the local population. We also explained that the decision as to whether or not underground storage of CO₂ will happen on a larger scale in the future goes beyond the scope of this project and will depend on other factors, such as political decision-making processes. In addition, we provided information on where the CO₂ could potentially be captured, how it could be transported, and how it could be stored offshore.

In the following, we present the results on the socio-political acceptance of CCUS as a technology option to mitigate climate change and on the community acceptance of its implementation. We first

present the overall results, taking into account the full samples, and then turn to the results broken down by different social groups.

5.2.1 OVERALL RESULTS ON THE (INFORMED) ACCEPTANCE OF CCUS

Based on the survey results across countries, **the socio-political acceptance of CCUS as a technology option to reduce CO₂ emissions is mixed** (see Figure 3). Respondents in the **Italian** regional and national sample **tend to evaluate this option rather positively**, with more than 70% of valid responses rating it as a good or very good option. There is no statistically significant difference in the response patterns between the two samples from Italy. This is different in Greece. While the evaluation by **the general public in Greece is rather positive**, with 48% evaluating CCUS as a good or very good option to mitigate climate change, **Eastern Macedonia and Thrace features the lowest share of positive ratings among all samples (40%)** and **the highest share of sceptical respondents (28%)**. In both the regional and the national samples, many respondents are undecided (>32%).

Figure 3: Overall evaluation of CCUS as a technology option to mitigate climate change.

In the national surveys, we asked study participants about their acceptance of implementing CCUS in the respective countries in general, i.e. in Greece or Italy. As can be seen in Figure 4, the acceptance of the implementation of CCUS in Greece and Italy in general by the respondents in the national surveys is around 70%. Thus, acceptance levels of its implementation in Italy are similar to the respondents' overall evaluation of CCUS, while in Greece they are considerably higher.

Figure 4: Acceptance of the potential implementation of CCUS in the respective countries.

Further, community acceptance of the local implementation of CCUS in the study areas was assessed. The results show similar patterns to its more general assessment as a technology option to mitigate climate change (see Figure 5). However, some differences can be observed. First, respondents in Greece tend to be more positive with regard to a potential local implementation of the technology in the respective study area, i.e. in Kavala and Thasos. In particular, at the national level, respondents reacted very positively, with 71% supporting an actual implementation of CCUS in the study area. This is comparable to the levels of acceptance in Italy, where 67% of respondents in the regional sample and 71% of the respondents in the national sample support the local implementation of CCUS in the respective study area, i.e. Emilia-Romagna. Second, although the share of Italian respondents that rate the local implementation of CCUS in Emilia-Romagna to be (rather) acceptable is lower than the share of respondents that evaluate the technology itself as (very) good, the share of respondents choosing the most positive category is higher with regard to a potential local implementation. Thus, the valid responses in Italy are similarly favourable towards the technology itself and its implementation in Emilia-Romagna. Finally, similar to the results for the overall evaluation of CCUS as a technology option to mitigate climate change, the lowest acceptance rate can be observed in Eastern Macedonia and Thrace. Here, 51% of the respondents rate the implementation of CCUS in Thasos and Kavala as (rather) acceptable. A further 26% of the respondents are undecided and 23% are against the local implementation of CCUS projects in Thasos and Kavala. Despite featuring the lowest acceptance ratings, also in this sample the responses are more positive than the ones related to the more general evaluation of the technology.

Overall, **it can be observed that the differences between the public perceptions in the regional and the national samples are more pronounced when referring to a potential local implementation of the technology** (community acceptance) in the respective study areas, rather than a more general evaluation of the technology (socio-political acceptance). With regard to a potential local implementation of CCUS, the differences between the responses at regional and local levels are

significant in a statistical sense in both countries, with the national samples being more supportive of the implementation. However, the differences are more substantial in Greece.

Figure 5: Acceptance of the potential implementation of CCUS in the respective study areas.

5.2.2 ACCEPTANCE OF CCUS ACROSS DIFFERENT SOCIAL GROUPS

In order to take into account differences between various social groups, we examined how these groups evaluated CCUS and to what extent their acceptance levels differed. To do this, we looked specifically at differences between genders, age groups, and types of residency. As detailed below, we find few statistically significant differences between different social groups across all samples.

For the gender comparison, we had to exclude the group of respondents that identified as non-binary, as the share of respondents in this group was very low, i.e. less than 1% in each sample (see Table 3). For female and male respondents, there are no clear differences in the socio-political acceptance of CCUS as an option to mitigate climate change in Eastern Macedonia and Thrace and in the two Italian samples. However, in the national sample in Greece, female respondents are statistically significantly more positive about the technology. In terms of community acceptance (see Figure 6), there appear to be slight tendencies towards higher levels of acceptance among men (particularly when comparing the most positive response category). However, the differences between the response patterns of the female and male respondents regarding their evaluation of the potential implementation of CCUS in the respective study areas is not statistically significant.

Figure 6: Acceptance of the potential implementation of CCUS in the respective study areas by gender.

Next, we present results on the differences in acceptance evaluations between the age groups used in the surveys. It should be noted, that in the national sample in Greece the share of respondents aged 70 years or older is comparatively small (see Table 3). Moreover, in Emilia-Romagna the small number of older individuals in the panel led to a modified definition of the two oldest categories, which limits the comparability with the other samples. To overcome this, we have therefore combined the two oldest age categories into one for our comparison of acceptance evaluations by age across all samples. Although this allows comparisons to be made between the different groups, the results for **the group of respondents aged 50 years or older must still be interpreted with caution**, particularly due to the low share of respondents in this group in the Greek sample.

Regarding both the socio-political acceptance of CCUS as a technology option to mitigate climate change and the community acceptance of its potential local implementation of CCUS in the respective study areas, we find statistically significant differences between the different age groups in Eastern Macedonia and Thrace. In both respects, the group of respondents aged 50 years or older differs statistically significantly from the other two age groups. While the share of respondents rating CCUS as a (very) good technology option for mitigating climate change is comparable across all age groups in the regional sample in Greece, the share of respondents rating the technology as (very) poor is comparatively high for the respondents aged 50 years or older (38%) compared to the two younger age groups (<18%). Similarly, the share of respondents aged 50 years or older that react negatively to a potential local implementation of CCUS in Kavala and Thasos (28%) is higher than in the two younger age groups (<19%). Furthermore, the share of respondents in support of the implementation of the technology in the study area is comparatively low in the group of respondents aged 50 years or older (45%), while more than 55% of the respondents in the two younger age groups consider the local implementation of CCUS in Kavala and Thasos to be (rather) acceptable. Further support for a trend towards higher levels of acceptance among younger respondents is provided by the national sample in Greece, where 77% of respondents between 18 and 29 years rating a potential local implementation of CCUS in Kavala and Thasos as (rather) acceptable, which is statistically significantly

higher than the other two age groups (see Figure 7). In the other samples, the response patterns do not differ significantly between age groups.

Figure 7: Acceptance of the potential implementation of CCUS in the respective study areas by age groups.

Finally, for the regional samples, we also looked at different types of residency, i.e. whether the respondents had their primary or secondary place of residency within the respective region. Similarly, for the national samples, we distinguished between those respondents that are currently or have previously lived in the respective study areas, and those who had never lived there. However, when comparing these groups of respondents in terms of their evaluation of the CCUS technology (socio-political acceptance) and their community acceptance of its implementation in the respective study areas or countries, no clear patterns emerge.

5.3 EXPECTED CHANGES RESULTING FROM AN IMPLEMENTATION OF CCUS

After assessing CCUS as a climate change mitigation option and reporting on their level of acceptance of its potential implementation in the respective study areas, respondents in all surveys were asked about their expectations regarding the changes this implementation would bring to the study areas. A distinction was made between expected overall changes (see Figure 8) and the expected environmental, economic, and societal changes (see Table 4).

Mirroring the findings on the socio-political acceptance of CCUS as an option to mitigate climate change and on the community acceptance of the local implementation of the technology in Thasos and Kavala and in Emilia-Romagna, the Italian samples (>72%) have the highest share of respondents expecting (very) positive overall changes as a result of a hypothetical implementation of CCUS in the respective study areas. Similarly, in Eastern Macedonia and Thrace, where community acceptance of CCUS is lowest, expectations regarding overall changes are the least positive compared to the other samples, with only 44% of respondents in Eastern Macedonia and Thrace expecting the overall changes following the potential implementation of CCUS in Thasos and Kavala to be positive. This compares to 27% of respondents in Eastern Macedonia and Thrace that expect the overall changes to be (rather)

negative. Finally, this sample also features a high share of undecided respondents, with 29% choosing the neutral option.

Figure 8: Expectations regarding the overall changes the implementation of CCUS might bring to the respective study areas.

While the reported expectations regarding the economic changes resulting from the potential implementation of CCUS in the respective study areas are largely consistent with the expectations regarding the overall changes, both the environmental and societal changes are expected to be less positive. For environment and society, the share of respondents in all samples expecting (very) positive changes is 8 to 20 percentage points lower than the share of respondents expecting the same regarding the overall changes. In all samples, **the differences between these more specific expectations and the more general expectations regarding overall changes are statistically significant.** In line with the results for the expectations regarding the overall changes, the respondents in Eastern Macedonia and Thrace were the most negative about all specific potential changes resulting from the implementation of the technology, with more than 23% expecting negative or very negative changes in Kavala and Thasos. In particular, environmental changes are expected to be (very) negative (36%). With regard to societal changes, the share of respondents expecting the changes to be neutral is rather high in all samples, ranging from 28% in Italy to 37% in Eastern Macedonia and Thrace.

Table 4: Expectations regarding different types of changes that the implementation of CCUS might bring to the respective study areas. Combined relative frequencies for the categories 'positive' and 'very positive' are displayed.

Positive expectations regarding ...	Eastern Macedonia and Thrace	Greece	Emilia-Romagna	Italy
... environmental changes	35%	49%	63%	65%
... economic changes	45%	60%	65%	71%
... societal changes	34%	43%	75%	61%

In addition to the rating items previously described, respondents in all samples were asked to indicate their positive or negative expectations regarding the potential deployment of CCUS in their respective regions by answering an open-ended question. For the analysis of the respective data, the responses were categorised into positive, neutral, and negative expectations. Some responses were included in more than one category, e.g. if they contained both positive and negative aspects.

The categorisation of the answers provided revealed that, across the samples, the most common positive expectations relate to the contribution of CCUS to reducing CO₂ emissions and the overall positive environmental impact that the implementation of this technology could have. In addition, local benefits are expected, particularly in terms of economic prospects. Of the responses categorised as neutral, the most common was a request for more information in order to make a more informed judgement. In terms of negative expectations about the potential implementation of CCUS in the respective study areas, many respondents cited safety and environmental concerns. Many also expressed a lack of trust in the actors involved. Overall, **a large number of respondents did not answer the open-ended question on their expectations regarding the hypothetical implementation of CCUS in the respective study areas**, although the share of missing values varies between the samples. In Italy, more than 72% of respondents answered this question, while in both the regional and national samples in Greece, the share of valid answers was lowest at under 48%.

Comparing the responses between the different samples, it can be seen that in Eastern Macedonia and Thrace a comparatively high share of responses are related to the environmental and local economic benefits of CCUS (45 out of 233 valid responses each). However, there is also a considerable share of negative aspects mentioned, such as environmental concerns (35 out of 233 valid responses) or safety concerns (20 out of 233 valid responses). The responses in the national survey in Greece follow a similar pattern. In the two samples in Italy, most respondents provided neutral answers.

5.4 ACCEPTANCE CONDITIONS

A mixture of open-ended and closed questions was used in the questionnaires in order to gain insight into the preferences for measures that should accompany the implementation of CCUS in order for it to be acceptable. The open-ended questions were presented before the three items with the pre-defined measures.

The results of the open-ended questions show that **the reassurance that sufficient safety measures will be taken in the process can be considered an important precondition for the implementation of CCUS in the study areas to be perceived as acceptable**. This is particularly pronounced in the two Greek samples, with 191 of the 287 valid responses in the regional sample and 432 of the 678 valid responses in the national sample highlighting the relevance of this measure. Another important theme that emerged was the demand for transparent information throughout the process. Interestingly, this was mainly mentioned in the two Italian samples. In Emilia-Romagna, it was cited in 110 of the 305 valid responses and in the national sample in Italy, it was cited in 249 of the 637 valid responses. In both samples the demand for transparent information was mentioned even more often than the safety measures, which was a dominant theme in Greece.

In addition to the open-ended question, the respondents in all samples were also given the opportunity to rate the importance of specific measures accompanying the implementation of CCUS in the respective study areas. One of these was the economic compensation for municipalities (see Figure 9). For this measure, respondents in all samples, and particularly in the national sample in Greece, expressed a high preference, with more than 72% of respondents in Greece considering the economic compensation for municipalities to be (very) important.

Figure 9: Perceived importance of the economic compensation for municipalities as a condition for acceptance.

The other two accompanying measures queried were municipal advisory boards to keep the public informed (see Figure 10)³ and active citizen engagement in decision making related to the implementation process (see Figure 11).

Figure 10: Perceived importance of municipal advisory boards to keep the public informed as a condition for acceptance.

³ In the Italian surveys, the wording of the question was slightly modified when translated into Italian and translates as 'events organised by the municipality in which experts inform citizens'.

Figure 11: Perceived importance of active citizen engagement in decision making as a condition for acceptance.

A comparison of the measures presented above indicates that all samples feature similar patterns of responses to the specific conditions for acceptance queried. Furthermore, respondents in all regions attach great importance to accompanying the implementation with all the measures listed. This is particularly true for the national sample in Greece. The share of respondents that consider municipal advisory boards to keep the public informed and active citizen engagement in decision making to be (very) important is highest in the national sample in Greece, at 81% each. The most important measure for respondents in all samples appears to be a measure to regularly inform the general public about the status quo and the process of a potential CCUS implementation. This is particularly valued in Italy, both in the regional and national samples, which is in line with the results for the respective open-ended question. In the Greek samples, the active engagement of citizens in decision making processes is also considered highly relevant. In all samples, economic compensation for the municipalities in the study areas appears to be relatively less important.

5.5 EXPECTATIONS REGARDING THE PROCESS

In terms of their expectations regarding a potential process of implementing CCUS in the respective study areas, the respondents were asked to rate the extent to which they would expect the corresponding decisions to be fair, indicating the expected legitimacy of the implementation process, and how likely they estimate an actual implementation in these areas would be.

With regard to the perceived process legitimacy of a hypothetical CCUS implementation in the respective study areas (see Figure 12), Italian respondents expressed more positive expectations regarding the fairness of this decision compared to the Greek samples. 65% of Italian respondents in both the regional and national sample expect a hypothetical future implementation of CCUS to be fair or very fair, with over 20% choosing the highest option — thus expecting it to be very fair. In the national sample in Greece, the share of respondents expecting a high degree of fairness in the decision to implement CCUS in the respective study area is also quite high, with 59% expecting the decision to be fair or very fair. However, most of this share is respondents stating the process to be fair, as the share of respondents choosing the highest category, i.e. expecting the decision on the implementation to be very fair, is comparatively low (9%). Respondents in Eastern Macedonia and

Thrace appear to be the most sceptical compared to the other samples. While 40% of the respondents expect the decision to be (very) fair, a further 27% expect it to be only moderately fair. This sample also features a high share of rather negative expectations, with 32% of respondents in this sample expecting the process to be only slightly fair or even unfair.

Figure 12: Expected fairness of the decision on the hypothetical implementation of CCUS in the respective study areas.

In the surveys, we asked about the expected likelihood of an actual implementation of CCUS in the respective study areas (see Figure 13). This was queried in all samples except Eastern Macedonia and Thrace, where the questionnaire was shorter than in the other samples due to the combination of phone and online sampling. Overall, the respondents appear to be largely undecided about the likelihood of CCUS actually being implemented in the respective study areas, with more than 37% choosing the neutral option. Respondents in the national sample in Italy were most optimistic about the likelihood of the implementation. Here, 41% thought it was very likely or rather likely.

Figure 13: Expected likelihood of an actual implementation of CCUS in the respective study areas.

5.6 TRUST IN SOCIETAL STAKEHOLDERS

Participants in the survey were asked to provide feedback on their level of trust in various societal stakeholders that could potentially be relevant in the context of a hypothetical deployment of CCUS in the respective study areas. These included industry actors, different levels of government from municipal to EU level, NGOs, scientists, and regional trade unions. Participants were asked to indicate their level of trust, with scores ranging from 1 ('no trust') to 5 ('complete trust').

We find that scientists are the most trusted group in each sample, with mean scores above 3.5. Furthermore, the results show that the level of trust attributed to each stakeholder group varies considerably (see Figure 14). In both the regional and national sample in Greece as well as in Emilia-Romagna, the national government is not highly trusted, with mean scores of below 2.6. In Greece, the sub-national levels of government also have comparatively low levels of trust, while the European Commission has higher levels of trust. In the two samples in Italy, the opposite is true. Finally, in both samples in Greece, industry actors and NGOs are trusted comparatively little. The same applies to regional trade unions in the Italian samples.

Overall, **it can be observed that, on average, the respondents in the national sample in Italy have the most trust in the stakeholder groups queried**, with a mean score of 3 across all actor groups. However, the difference to the other three samples is not very pronounced, as the average in all samples is above 2.7.

Figure 14: Mean score of trust in societal stakeholders for each actor group per sample, with scores ranging from 1 ('no trust') to 5 ('complete trust').

5.7 PREFERRED INVOLVEMENT OF SOCIETAL STAKEHOLDERS

In addition to assessing their trust in societal stakeholders, respondents were also asked to indicate their preferences for the potential involvement of societal stakeholders if CCUS were to be implemented in the study areas. Here, preferences for the involvement of the same group of stakeholders as in the question about trust were queried (see Section 5.6). Scores ranged from 1 ('not involved') to 3 ('very involved'). The questionnaire distinguished between the involvement of the different stakeholders as initiators (see Figure 15) and as decision makers (see Figure 16). It has to be noted that these questions were not asked in the regional survey in Greece due to the need of a shorter questionnaire.

Both for initiating the implementation of CCUS and for the decision making in this process, it can be observed that in every sample where the respective questions were asked, scientists are the most preferred group to be involved in the implementation of CCUS. This is in line with the results on trust in the different stakeholder groups. Also similar in all samples, NGOs are not seen as very important stakeholders that need to be involved either in initiating or in decision-making related to the implementation of CCUS. In the Italian regional and national sample, the potential involvement of regional trade unions in the implementation process is not considered as important as the involvement of other stakeholders. Preferences for the involvement of the other groups queried were at comparable levels. Respondents from the two Italian samples expressed a stronger preference for the involvement of industry actors and (sub)national government actors than Greek respondents. The involvement of the European Commission in the implementation process was rated similarly important in all samples.

Figure 15: Mean score of preferred involvement of societal stakeholders as initiators for each actor group per sample, with scores ranging from 1 ('not involved') to 3 ('very involved').

Figure 16: Mean score of preferred involvement of societal stakeholders as decision makers for each actor group per sample, with scores ranging from 1 ('not involved') to 3 ('very involved').

5.8 PREFERENCES FOR ALTERNATIVE APPROACHES

By evaluating CCUS against alternative approaches to mitigating climate change, we gained insight into which alternatives respondents considered to be better, equal, or worse options compared to CCUS. This question was asked in all samples except Eastern Macedonia and Thrace (see Figure 17). While **more reforestation and afforestation is seen as the most preferable method of mitigating climate change among the methods presented, using more photovoltaics,**

HERCCULES

full CCUS chain demonstration

strengthening energy efficiency, and promoting the implementation of green hydrogen technologies were seen as slightly better options than CCUS. Building more onshore and offshore wind parks was also favoured over CCUS, although to a lesser extent. The item related to having more sufficient/sustainable lifestyles was rated considerably more positively by respondents in the two Italian samples than in the Greek sample. However, this could also be partly due to the fact that the Greek version of the questionnaire refers to 'sufficient lifestyles', as originally planned, whereas the Italian version refers to 'sustainable lifestyles', due to the lack of suitable and generally understandable translations of the term 'sufficient'. This needs to be considered in the interpretation of the findings on this question.

Methods of mitigating climate change that were rated similarly favourable compared to CCUS were more high voltage lines and more demand pricing — which was preferred to CCUS in the two Italian samples, but evaluated slightly worse than CCUS in the Greek sample. Increasing the share of nuclear energy was seen as an equal option to CCUS in the two Italian samples and slightly worse in the Greek sample. Higher energy prices were considered slightly worse than CCUS by respondents in all samples. This option was thus evaluated the most negative.

Preferred alternatives for climate change mitigation (compared to CCUS)

Figure 17: Mean score of preferred alternatives for mitigating climate change per sample, compared to CCUS, with scores ranging from -2 ('worse option') to 2 ('better option').

5.9 FURTHER ATTITUDES AND SENTIMENTS OF THE RESPONDENTS

To better understand respondents' attitudes towards the potential implementation of CCUS in the respective study areas, we included questions about their perception regarding climate change, their attachment to their area, and their attitudes towards energy-intensive industries. We also assessed what they considered to be the key topics of concern in the regions/countries surveyed. These insights are expected to help provide a more comprehensive reflection of the attitudes and sentiments of

people in the respective study areas, which might be relevant in a potential further exploration of CCUS implementation in the study areas (see Section 6).

5.9.1 PERCEPTION REGARDING CLIMATE CHANGE

The majority of respondents (>79%) in all samples surveyed describe climate change as a severe or very severe problem (see Figure 18). More than 39% even chose the highest category, thus perceiving climate change as a very severe problem. The share of respondents who see climate change as a moderate problem is between 11% and 14%, while the share of those who see it as a mild or no problem is below 9% in all samples.

Figure 18: Perception regarding climate change.

5.9.2 PLACE ATTACHMENT

In order to assess the respondents' attachment to the area in which they live and to gain a better understanding of how the regions surveyed differ in this respect, we included several items on this topic in the regional questionnaires. However, due to the shorter duration of the survey in Eastern Macedonia and Thrace, only two of the four items were included in the respective questionnaires. Thus, only these two items are presented below.

Looking at the level of place attachment of the respondents in Eastern Macedonia and Thrace and in Emilia-Romagna, it becomes apparent that in both regional samples the measured levels are quite high. In Eastern Macedonia and Thrace, 69% feel strongly or very strongly attached to the area they live in, and in Emilia-Romagna the share is even higher, with 81% feeling (very) strongly attached (see Figure 20). In both samples, when asked whether they feel very attached to the area where they live, only less than 8% of respondents disagree or strongly disagree.

Figure 19: The regional surveys respondents' attachment to the area they live in.

As this is likely to be closely related to the place attachment of respondents in the regional surveys, we also asked respondents to indicate how long they had lived in the area of their place of residence (see Figure 19). While in both samples the majority of respondents had lived in their respective area for 20 years or more, the share was actually higher in Eastern Macedonia and Thrace (76%) than in Emilia-Romagna (64%), despite comparatively lower place attachment in the former region.

Figure 20: Time lived at the place of residence in the regional samples.

5.9.3 ATTITUDES TOWARDS ENERGY-INTENSIVE INDUSTRIES

To gain an understanding of the prevailing attitudes towards energy-intensive industries in the samples, the respondents to our surveys were asked to rate the economic importance of these industries in their region or country. To clarify which industries are considered energy-intensive and therefore relevant for the capture, utilisation, or storage of CO₂, we provided examples of relevant industries in the region or country.

When asked about their attitudes towards energy-intensive industries (see Figure 21), between 72% and 79% of respondents in all samples indicated that they consider energy-intensive industries to be economically important or very important in their region or country. While in three of the four samples, 38% of the respondents even chose the highest category and thus considered energy-intensive industries to be very important in their region or country, the corresponding share was lower in Eastern Macedonia and Thrace (29%).

Figure 21: Perceived economic importance of energy-intensive industries in the respective region or country.

In terms of employment in the specific energy-intensive industries relevant to the respective region or country (see Figure 22), the importance of the specified energy-intensive industries as employers appears to be comparable between the samples, with up to 3% of respondents themselves working in these industries and up to 6% having family members working in these industries.

Figure 22: Occupation in energy-intensive industries. Multiple selections possible.

5.9.4 TOPICS OF CONCERN

Figure 23 presents topics that might concern the region or country under study, and depicts the mean of the respondents' importance evaluations for the specified topics. The list of items was based on survey items created by the Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation, Nuclear Safety and Consumer Protection (2022) and adapted to the regional and national contexts of this research. The respective question was not asked in Eastern Macedonia and Thrace.

Most relevant for this study is the respondents' perception of environmental and climate protection, as it is most likely to be linked to their acceptance of CCUS. This topic was considered important in both the national sample in Greece and the two Italian samples, with mean scores between 4.2 and 4.5 – on a scale ranging from 1 ('unimportant') to 5 ('very important'). In the two Italian samples, environmental and climate protection was one of the most important topics for the respondents to our surveys, surpassed only by the item related to the state of the healthcare system, and receiving scores roughly comparable to or higher than several of the other topics queried. In contrast, in the Greek sample, several topics are considered more important than environmental and climate protection, including the state of the healthcare and of the education system, unemployment, economic development, crime and public safety, and social justice. Thus, despite comparable mean scores for environmental and climate protection in all samples, the relative importance of this topic appears to be higher in the two Italian samples and lower in Greece.

Figure 23: Mean score of the perceived importance of topics that might concern the region or country under study, ranging from 1 ('unimportant') to 5 ('very important').

5.10 UNCERTAINTY IN THE RESPONSE BEHAVIOURS

The shares of respondents reported in the text and the figures throughout this report refer only to valid responses, i.e. excluding missing values and 'don't know' responses. If taken into account, the missing values would decrease the respective shares accordingly.

When looking at the questions regarding the respondents' socio-political acceptance of CCUS as a technology option to mitigate climate change and their community acceptance of its implementation in the study areas, it should be noted that up to 12% of the respondents chose the 'don't know' option. The share of respondents choosing this option for these items was slightly higher in the regional surveys compared to the baseline national survey results. Compared to other questions in the surveys, the share of missing values is quite high for these items and for several other items related to the potential implementation of the technology, e.g. in terms of potential impacts on the study areas or preferences for alternatives. This reflects the low level of respondents' familiarity with the technology.

6 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

CCUS is high on the political agenda and national governments and the EU are communicating ambitious targets for its implementation (European Commission, 2024a). However, the policy framework is still evolving (Dütschke & Duscha, 2022; see also D8.1 from HERCCULES) and questions of social acceptance of the technology remain unanswered.

To address this issue of acceptance, this deliverable investigated in detail the state of community acceptance of CCUS in the current situation of increasing political and industrial interest in the topic. Moreover, the report also related findings on community acceptance to those on socio-political acceptance. The aim is to provide input for the development of a participation and engagement strategy within the project by providing survey based insights on the current state of familiarity with and acceptance of CCUS technologies, as well as on related factors in the relevant regions, Kavala and Thasos (part of the Eastern Macedonia and Thrace region in Greece) and Emilia-Romagna (in Italy). As outlined in Section 3.4 of this deliverable, few previous studies have examined the two countries,

Greece and Italy, and none — to the best of our knowledge — the same regions, i.e. Eastern Macedonia and Thrace (Greece) and Emilia-Romagna (Italy).

State of public perceptions of CCUS technologies

In line with the state of research (see section 3.1), we find **low levels of familiarity** with CCUS for all samples analysed, with 41-56% of the respondents indicating that they have never heard of it. Overall, Italians categorise themselves as somewhat more familiar than Greek respondents. **The results indicate that the socio-political acceptance of CCUS as a technology option to reduce CO₂ emissions is mixed. Italian respondents tend to evaluate CCUS technologies as an option to mitigate climate change rather positively** in the regional and national sample, with more than **70%** of valid responses rating it as a **good or very good option**. In **Greece**, there is some **variance in the responses** in the two samples. While the evaluation on the **national level in Greece** is still **rather positive**, with **48%** evaluating CCUS as a good or very good option to mitigate climate change, **Eastern Macedonia and Thrace** features the **lowest share of positive ratings** among all samples (**40%**) and the highest share of sceptical respondents (28%). In both the regional and the national samples, many respondents are undecided (>32%), which is likely related to the low familiarity of the respondents with CCUS. It is important to note that the Emilia-Romagna study area is larger than the Eastern Macedonia and Thrace area from which the study participants were recruited. This means that respondents from the Greek regional sample may have been more critical because they live closer to the storage site.

With regard to a **local implementation, community acceptance** in the surveys is quite high, with the share of respondents rating a potential implementation of CCUS in the respective study area as **rather acceptable or acceptable**. While levels of acceptance for local implementation are **lower in Eastern Macedonia and Thrace (51%)**, we find comparable levels of acceptance in the other three samples, i.e. **67% of respondents in Emilia-Romagna** and 71% of respondents in the two national samples (rather) accepting a potential local implementation of the technology.

Few differences regarding acceptance emerge in relation to socio-demographic variables, with men and women holding very similar opinions (only in the national sample in Greece women are significantly more positive towards a potential local implementation of CCUS than men). In Italy, we found no difference between age groups. In Greece, we find that in Eastern Macedonia and Thrace older people are more sceptical and younger respondents are more favourable on the national level.

Insights for the development of public engagement and participation strategies

For Italy and, more specifically, Emilia-Romagna, the surveys point to a positive situation to start with engagement and participation around CCUS technologies. In Greece, especially in the relevant region of Eastern Macedonia and Thrace, current opinions are somewhat less supporting; nevertheless, a majority of respondents in the Greek region spontaneously supported a local development of CCUS. This needs to be interpreted in light of low levels of familiarity, which means that the acceptance levels measured in the surveys are most likely spontaneous reactions and not informed decisions. This also implies that they will likely develop in a dynamic way.

Further insights from the surveys include the finding that, across samples, large majorities of respondents (>80%) see the need of tackling climate change as an important issue for today's societies. As CCUS has the potential to make a contribution to climate change mitigation, this can be used in discussions around it. Nevertheless, it is relevant to note, that respondents see an extensive list of other challenges to societies, such as economic development, public safety, public health, and social justice (see Figure 23). This means that they will also pay attention to these issues, potentially limiting their resources to follow discussions around CCUS or connecting other societal and political

challenges with the discussion on CCUS. Thus, debates around CCUS could take up potential contributions or tensions with these other relevant topics, e.g. by considering the role of CCUS in securing employment or by being sensitive to social justice issues.

The survey results show that CCUS is placed between other options to mitigate climate change and that, for example, re- and afforestation, renewables or energy efficiency, as well as the development of a hydrogen economy are favoured compared to CCUS while options leading to higher energy prices are declined (see Figure 17). Therefore, it could be useful to explain in discussions around CCUS how this technology aligns with these other options and what expected contributions of all of them are to mitigate climate change in a cost-efficient way.

The current discussion on CCUS sees the technologies mainly in relation to hard-to-abate industries (see the Communication by the European Commission (2024b) on an industrial carbon management strategy). This is in line with survey respondents' feedback that a large majority (>75%) see energy intensive industries as important for the respective region or country (see Figure 21). This line of argument could be further strengthened by outlining the role of CCUS in mitigating climate change together with alternative options, as outlined in the previous paragraph.

With regard to the specific design of public engagement and participation strategies, the survey provides insight into who trusted actors are (see sections 5.6 and 5.7). Here, scientists stand out. Italian respondents on the national level are also trusting policymakers on the regional and municipal level while in Greece regional trade unions are some of the most trusted actors. More generally, involving local government actors into CCUS developments was supported by a majority of survey participant as well as the need to engage citizens, which was seen as highly important, especially in both samples in Greece (see section 5.4). Another issue the surveys brought to light is that across samples, majorities of respondents consider economic compensation for communities as relevant in case of CCUS development (see section 5.4).

Overall, the need for a high-quality engagement strategy is even higher in Eastern Macedonia and Thrace — given higher levels of scepticism towards CCUS in the region, lower trust that an implementation will follow a fair process (see Figure 12), and a higher emphasis on the need for citizen engagement from respondents.

Conclusions

Previous research has pointed out that community acceptance emerges under the influence and interaction of a variety of factors, only some of which are within the discretion of project developers or in the hands of an EU project consortium (see Oltra at al., 2012, for relevant factors and section 3.3 of this deliverable). Within WP8 of HERCCULES, D8.1 provided additional insights into the political process and D8.2 explored community characteristics. Before designing a strategy for public engagement and participation, these additional insights need to be taken into account in addition to the survey results. Based on the survey, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- Policy and industry actions should address low awareness and promote discussion of CCUS technologies.
- The discussion on CCUS should embed CCUS pathways more broadly in societal issues and other climate change mitigation options.
- The involvement of citizens and local authorities is very important and should be emphasised.
- Confidence-building measures are needed through highly transparent communication and consideration of the involvement of scientists as the most trusted actors.
- Regional differences need to be taken into account — for the specific implications of this conclusion the insights from D8.2 are particularly important.

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8 ANNEX

Table A1: Survey items and valid item response categories for the items that form the common identical core of the questionnaires of all surveys in English language, exemplified by questions from the regional survey of Eastern Macedonia and Thrace.

Topics in the questionnaire	Survey item
Socio-economic variables	I1: Where do you live? (response categories refer to the NUTS3 regions in Eastern Macedonia and Thrace)
	I2a: Is this your primary place of residence? (yes – no)
	[If I2a = 'no'] I2b: Where is your primary place of residence? (open-ended)
	I3: Please indicate your gender. (i) Male; (ii) Female; (iii) None of the above
	I4: What is your age group? (i) Under 18; (ii) 18-29 years; (iii) 30-49 years; (iv) 50-69 years; (v) 70 years or older
	I5: What is your highest level of education? (i) Less than primary and primary education; (ii) Lower secondary education and upper secondary education; (iii) Tertiary education
	I6: How would you describe your household's current income? Please choose the answer that best describes how you manage on your household's current income. (i) Finding it very difficult to manage on current income; (ii) Finding it difficult to manage on current income; (iii) Coping on current income; (iv) Managing comfortably on current income; (v) Managing very comfortably on current income
Place attachment ^a	I7: Do you or anyone in your family work for the petroleum industry? (multiple selections possible) (i) Yes, I work in this industry; (ii) Yes, someone from my family works in it; (iii) No
	I8: How long have you lived in your current area? (i) Less than 1 year; (ii) 1 to 4 years; (iii) 5 to 9 years; (iv) 10 to 14 years; (v) 15 to 19 years; (vi) 20 years and more
	I9: To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following [statement] about the area where you live? I am very attached to

	the area. (strongly disagree – disagree – neutral – agree – strongly agree)
Topics of concern ^b	<p>[Example from the questionnaire for the Emilia-Romagna survey:] On the following list you will find topics that might concern Emilia-Romagna today. Please indicate in each case how important or unimportant you consider the following topics to be for Emilia-Romagna. (unimportant – slightly important – moderately important – important – very important)</p> <p>I10: Crime, public safety I11: Development of urban and rural areas I12: Digitisation I13: Economic development I14: Environmental and climate protection I15: Immigration, integration I16: Social justice I17: State of the healthcare system I18: State of the education system I19: Unemployment I20: Wars, terrorism</p>
Perception regarding climate change	<p>I21: Please choose one of the following options. Climate change is...</p> <p>(i) ... not a problem; (ii) ... a mild problem; (iii) ... a moderate problem; (iv) ... a severe problem; (v) ... a very severe problem.</p>
Attitudes towards industry	<p>I22: In your opinion, what is the economic importance of energy-intensive industry (e.g. petroleum) in Kavala and Thasos? (unimportant – slightly important – moderately important – important – very important)</p>
Familiarity with CCUS	<p>I23a: Have you ever heard of Carbon Capture, Utilisation, and Storage (CCUS)?</p> <p>(i) No, I have never heard of it; (ii) Yes, but I don't really know what it is (iii) Yes, I have heard of it and I know what it is</p> <p>[If I23a = ii or iii] I13b: Where did you hear of it? (open-ended)</p>
(Informed) acceptance of CCUS	<p>I24: How would you rate this option to tackle climate change? (very poor – poor – neutral – good – very good)</p>

	<p>I25: How acceptable would it be for you if CCUS were actually implemented in Kavala and Thasos? (unacceptable – rather unacceptable – neutral – rather acceptable – acceptable)</p>
<p>Expected impacts of CCUS implementation</p>	<p>I26: When thinking about the overall changes the implementation of CCUS could bring to Kavala and Thasos, do you think they would be ...? (very negative – negative – neutral – positive – very positive)</p> <p>What do you think? (very negative – negative – neutral – positive – very positive)</p> <p>I27: The environmental impacts of CCUS in Kavala and Thasos would be...</p> <p>I28: The economic impacts of CCUS in Kavala and Thasos would be...</p> <p>I29: The societal impacts of CCUS in Kavala and Thasos would be...</p>
<p>Acceptance conditions</p>	<p>I30: What measures should CCUS be accompanied by in order to be acceptable? (open-ended)</p> <p>In order for CCUS to be acceptable, to what extent would you consider the following measures important? (unimportant – slightly important – moderately important – important – very important)</p> <p>I31: Economic compensation of the municipalities</p> <p>I32: Municipal advisory boards to keep the public informed</p> <p>I33: Active citizen engagement in decision making</p>
<p>Preferences for alternative approaches^b</p>	<p>[Example from the questionnaire for the Emilia-Romagna survey:]</p> <p>To what extent do you consider the following options more suitable for tackling climate change (compared to CCUS)? (... is a worse option. – ... is a slightly worse option. – ... is an equal option. – ... is a slightly better option. – ... is a better option.)</p> <p>I34: Building more on-shore/off-shore wind parks...</p> <p>I35: Having more sufficient lifestyles...</p> <p>I36: Higher energy prices...</p> <p>I37: Increasing the share of nuclear energy...</p> <p>I38: More demand pricing...</p> <p>I39: More high voltage lines...</p> <p>I40: More reforestation and afforestation...</p>

	<p>I41: Promoting the implementation of green</p> <p>I42: hydrogen technologies...</p> <p>I43: Strengthening energy efficiency...</p> <p>I44: Using more photovoltaic...</p>
Expectations regarding the process	<p>I45: To what extent do you think the decisions about implementing CCUS in Kavala and Thasos would be fair? (unfair – slightly fair – moderately fair – fair – very fair)</p> <p>[Example from the questionnaire for the Emilia-Romagna survey:]</p> <p>I46^b: How likely do you think it is that CCUS will actually be implemented in Emilia-Romagna? (very unlikely – rather unlikely – half/half – rather likely – very likely)</p>
Trust in societal stakeholders	<p>I47: How much would you trust the following actors to make good decisions about the implementation of CCUS in Kavala and Thasos? (no trust – little trust – moderate trust – trust – complete trust)</p> <p>(i) Industry (petroleum industry); (ii) Municipality; (iii) Regional unit; (iv) Region; (v) Greek State; (vi) European Commission; (vii) NGOs; (viii) Scientists; (ix) Regional trade unions</p>
Preferred involvement of societal stakeholders	<p>[Example from the questionnaire for the Emilia-Romagna survey:]</p> <p>I48^b: To what extent would you like to see the following actors involved in initiating the implementation of CCUS in Emilia-Romagna? (not involved – moderately involved – very involved)</p> <p>(i) Industry; (ii) Municipality; (iii) Province; (iv) Region; (v) Italian State; (vi) European Commission; (vii) NGOs; (viii) Scientists; (ix) Regional trade unions</p> <p>[Example from the questionnaire for the Emilia-Romagna survey:]</p> <p>I49^b: To what extent would you like to see the following actors involved in the decision-making regarding the implementation of CCUS in Emilia-Romagna? (not involved – moderately involved – very involved)</p> <p>(i) Industry; (ii) Municipality; (iii) Province; (iv) Region; (v) Italian State; (vi) European Commission; (vii) NGOs; (viii) Scientists; (ix) Regional trade unions</p>
Preferred involvement in the process ^a	<p>I50: Would you like to be involved if the option of implementing CCUS were explored further in Emilia-Romagna? (multiple selections possible)</p>

HERCCULES

full CCUS chain demonstration

	(i) I would not like to be involved; (ii) I would like to receive information; (iii) I would like to be able to express my views on the project; (iv) I would like to actively participate in the decision making
	I51: Would you like to participate in workshops or events related to CCUS? (yes – no)

^a Only used in the regional surveys.

^b Not used in Eastern Macedonia and Thrace.